

Astrometry of Small Solar System Objects with NOT

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Abstract

Telescopes of the 2 – 4 meter class such as the NOT can be an extremely important observational asset for the field of small solar system objects, thanks to a combination of large aperture and typically easier access compared to 8 – 10 meter class instruments, especially on short notice.

At the same time, the field of small bodies is characterized by the more rapid timescales on which objects change their observability circumstances. The motion of the object, both in the plane of the sky and in topocentric distance, induces observational constraints that are different from most other fields of astronomy: observability windows may be very short, pointing and tracking can become more complex, and an increased importance must be placed on the temporal accuracy of observations.

In this contribution we will present a couple of interesting results that show how NOT can provide valuable astrometric observations with good angular and temporal precision.

We will show how the telescope can provide high-precision astrometry of a challenging moving object down to magnitude ~ 25 , a faintness level that is often assumed to be the prerogative of 8 – 10 meter class instruments.

We will also briefly present how we took advantage of an international observing campaign to verify the timing accuracy of the system, another important parameter for the usability of the telescope on fast moving objects.

Keywords: astrometry, small solar system bodies, near-Earth objects.

1 Introduction

In this contribution, we will briefly outline the importance of high-precision astrometry for the study of small bodies in our Solar System, focusing in particular on specific observational opportunities that a telescope like the Nordic Optical Telescope (NOT) can fully exploit.

Our analysis will mostly focus on astrometric observations, and on how they enable our dynamical understanding of asteroid, comets and other small bodies.

The discussion will show that telescopes of a few meters in size are capable of producing extremely valuable detections, often in a temporal and brightness regime that is hardly explored by other smaller or larger facilities.

2 Small bodies of the Solar System

The so-called Small Solar System Objects are all minor bodies in our planetary system that are not proper planets. This overall class of objects includes different types of bodies:

- Asteroids: mostly rocky and inactive bodies, of various dynamical origins and orbital classes, located and originated in various regions of the Solar System.

- Comets: typically icy bodies rich of volatiles, in general generating in the outer region of our planetary system.
- Transneptunian objects: large outer Solar System bodies, including massive objects that are often classified as dwarf planets.
- Planetary satellites: orbiting any of the eight major planets of our Solar System.
- Meteoroids: smaller sub-meter, and often millimeter or micrometer sized grains, that orbit the Solar System on typically asteroidal or cometary orbit, and are often the byproduct of outgassing uplift or fragmentation of other bodies. They are typically too small to observe while in space, and they are studied only during their atmospheric entry as meteor events.

In this discussion, we will mostly focus on asteroids, the most numerous telescopically-observable class. Nevertheless, the large majority of what we will discuss also applies to other bodies (comets in particular), although in some cases extra details may need to be considered.

Furthermore, we will mostly focus the discussion on imaging observations obtained with ground-based telescopes like NOT, and only in the visual wavelength range, where astrometry is typically performed.

3 Astrometry

In the context of asteroidal and cometary bodies, the word “astrometry” is typically intended in the absolute sense, i.e. the determination of 4 properties:

- Absolute coordinates in the plane of the sky (right ascension and declination) of an object of interest.
- The precise determination of the instant of time of the observation, a crucial piece of information for objects that are moving on timescales that are much shorter than those of other astrophysical phenomena.
- The accurate location of the observing station from where the observation is made, since the distances in play are such that parallax effects are easily noticeable.
- An estimate of the uncertainties of all the parameters above, essential information to be used when the data is analyzed.

The determination of these quantities is typically done on an optical image, either taken through a CCD sensor or, more recently, via CMOS arrays. The astrometric measurement in itself can be seen as the combination of two basic components:

- The “centroid” of the source corresponding to the target, i.e. the measurement of the source location in the pixel coordinate system of the array.
- The “astrometric solution”, i.e. the mapping of each pixel of the array to absolute sky coordinates.

3.1. Why is astrometry important?

Astrometry is often seen as a mere technical step in the localization of a target, while in reality it often has an extremely important scientific value, both directly and indirectly.

A first immediately obvious role is that it enables the follow-up of any newly discovered object. Without proper astrometry, all discovered small bodies will be lost within hours or days of their discovery, because it quickly becomes impossible to determine their long-term ephemeris on the basis of a short observed arc.

At the same time, the astrometric measurements and the orbit determination that is based on them is the most immediate way to determine the object's dynamical properties, and possibly its peculiarities. Only once an orbit is properly determined, it becomes possible to separate peculiar or unique targets from routine objects (e.g. main belt asteroids), and to decide if they warrant further scientific investigation. A properly determined orbit is also the basis for a study of the object's dynamics and past history, essential to understand its origin and its evolution in the dynamical history of our planetary system.

Furthermore, once a long observed arc is available on a specific object, its orbit determination becomes sensitive to subtle dynamical effects, such as radiation pressure accelerations, or the so-called Yarkovsky effect. The direct measurement of such dynamical anomalies provides physical information on the object itself, essential to understand its composition, structure, origin and evolution.

All of these reasons are of course purely “dynamical”, i.e. based on the study of the object's motion. However, it's important to remember that astrometry and orbit determination processes allow the determination of a precise ephemeris for each objects at future times. This information in turns allows the use of other observing techniques (e.g. spectroscopy, adaptive optics imaging, space-based observations) and instruments that require high-precision sub-arcsecond pointing. Without a good ephemeris, this entire science on small bodies would not be feasible.

And, last but not least, for the specific class of Near-Earth Objects (NEOs), those capable of coming close to the Earth and possibly resulting in an impact threat, astrometry provides the essential starting point for planetary defense activities. Close approach and impact predictions are directly based on astrometry, and the possible location of an impact point can only be confidently determined if the available astrometric measurements (and their error bars) can be trusted.

3.2. Role of different telescope classes in the field of astrometry

The current scenario of discovery, astrometry and dynamical study of asteroids, and NEOs in particular, is mostly dominated by four types of telescopic “players”, each one covering a specific role that develops on specific temporal timescales:

- The first type of players are the so-called “survey telescopes”. Today these are typically meter-scale telescopes that are often entirely dedicated to the task of discovering new small bodies. They are generally funded and tasked to optimize their observing strategy towards NEOs, but discovery of other small bodies are the obvious consequence of their task. These telescopes work as the “realtime” players: they survey the sky and locate unknown (and known) moving objects, in a mostly automated way. Their job typically ends at reporting the position of the objects they detect though. They are rarely tasked to do follow-up observations of anything they discover, unless if they re-observe them by chance in their scheduling pattern.
- The second important contributors to the scenario are what we can call “immediate follow-up” telescope. Those facilities are typically of very small size (typically sub-meter), and often operated by amateur astronomers. Their task is to reobserve recently discovered candidates as quickly as possible, preventing new discoveries from being lost. In most cases, for NEO discoveries, the timescales needed to successfully reobserve an object can be very short, sometimes hours or even minutes. The flexibility of these telescopes allows them to react to new potentially interesting candidates and quickly report confirmatory observations that are essential to firmly establish their orbits. Despite being smaller, they can often compensate their limiting magnitude

with the ability to observe for a longer time, allowing them to easily observe what a meter-class telescope discovered in a few minutes by dedicating overall observing times of the level of an hour.

- New NEOs are nowadays typically discovered in a magnitude range between 20 and 22, usually while they are having an unusually close approach with our planet. However, such conditions typically don't last very long: the newly discovered asteroid, first seen around close approach, soon recedes away from Earth, quickly becoming fainter. On the timescale of a few days to weeks, it becomes too faint for amateur telescopes to observe, reaching a magnitude range that is now only accessible with professional facilities. At this point, a capability for “extended follow-up” becomes essential, and can be provided by telescopes of a few meters in diameter, like NOT. They benefit from an often less tight schedule, which may allow ToO-like observations with an advance warning of a few days.
- The fourth and last role in the process is taken by specific facilities that can perform “deep follow-up”, i.e. observing objects at the very limit of what can currently be achieved. This includes the largest ground-based 10-meter-class telescopes, and space observatories such as HST and JWST. Time on such facilities is an extremely scarce resource, which can only be used in the case of extremely high-profile targets, observing them at the limit of what our technological capabilities can offer. These deep observations can often happen months or years after discovery, even when the target of interest is located very far from Earth, but are of course only performed when absolutely necessary, e.g. when an asteroid poses a high impact threat and timely observations can make a difference in the advance warning available before a possible future collision.

4 Small bodies at NOT

As said above, a telescope like NOT falls easily in the third general type presented above, i.e. it is an excellent instrument for what we can call “extended follow-up” opportunities. A good extended follow-up telescope needs to satisfy most, if not all, of these requirements:

- A significant aperture, to observe objects fainter than magnitude $\sim 22-25$ in a reasonably short time, or to magnitude ~ 26 in about an hour.
- The capability to observe objects that are not known at the time of the proposal (i.e., offer a ToO-like mode of operation).
- The availability of the telescope on reasonably short notice (days to a week or so).
- A good optical imager with good sensitivity.
- The ability to observe unfiltered to reach the faintest limiting magnitude.
- Excellent seeing, since the astrometric quality one can obtain scales (roughly quadratically) with the seeing.
- The ability to point low over the horizon.

These are all characteristics that NOT can offer to observers, making it an ideal instrument for astrometric follow-up of high-priority NEOs and other small Solar System objects.

Over the last few years we performed a few test observations and checks that allow us to fully understand the performances of the telescope on these specific aspects of an observations, and make it fully ready for astrometric use. We will now briefly report the results some of these tests.

4.1. Timing accuracy

In order to get valuable astrometry, it is necessary to ensure the accuracy of the timestamp that the telescope writes in the FITS header. We took the opportunity of an international timing campaign organized by the International Asteroid Warning Network (IAWN) to test the timing accuracy (Farnocchia et al., 2022) of the ALFOSC instrument at NOT.

We imaged a very fast moving asteroid, 2019 XS, during a particularly close approach in 2021. Due to the short distance, its sky motion was extremely fast for a few days around closest approach. At the same time, its orbit is known well enough that we could assume the object’s position in the sky to be very well known, and use it to “calibrate” the time of the telescope. At the end of the test, the ALFOSC system showed a stable time bias of $\sim +0.4$ s. This offset needs to be added to the timetag of any astrometric measurement from that instrument, in order to ensure proper sub-second timing accuracy to the resulting records.

4.2. Location

Getting an appropriate location for the telescope is also important, because small bodies are located at distances for which parallax effects over the scale of kilometers are usually noticeable (and, in some cases, also at meter-level).

In the past, observers extracting astrometry from images taken with NOT were often reporting it to the Minor Planet Center (MPC) using the generic IAU observatory code 950, labeled “La Palma”, and assigned to the overall observatory many decades ago. However, the actual location associated to this identifier is located about 500 m away from NOT, near the William Herschel Telescope (WHT). This level of inaccuracy is certainly insufficient for NEO astrometry.

In order to permanently solve the issue, we requested and obtained a dedicated IAU code from the NOT, which is now permanently associated to correct values for the latitude, longitude and altitude (above the ellipsoid) of the telescope. NOT is now uniquely identified with IAU code Z23, labeled “Nordic Optical Telescope, La Palma”. Anybody producing astrometry from NOT data can now associate their measurements to this code, ensuring a proper identification of the observing point.

4.3. Limiting magnitude (and an example of NEO science with NOT)

On 2020 February 15 the Catalina Sky Survey in Arizona, USA, discovered a new asteroid. Within a few hours it became clear that the object was extremely close, and already the following day it became evident that the object was actually in Earth’s orbit. This asteroid, later designated 2020 CD3, is the second-known “temporarily captured object”, a natural body that, for a certain amount of time, enters in orbit around the Earth as a sort of small and temporary moonlet.

A team of astronomers (Fedorets et al., 2020; Naidu et al., 2021) used NOT to obtain rapid high precision astrometry, starting less than a week after discovery and ensuring nearly weekly observational coverage for the subsequent months. NOT proved capable of obtaining excellent astrometric accuracy, at the level of $\pm 0.1''$ or better. It was capable of following the object until it became fainter than magnitude 25, the last telescope to detect the object after it left Earth.

The astrometric work of NOT on 2020 CD3 exemplifies the kind of observational regimes that are typical of NEO observations. Contrary to other fields of astronomy, astrometry “only” requires to detect the object, and low Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) detections are often sufficient to extract valuable information.

As an example, the last-ever detection of 2020 CD3, one month after it left Earth’s orbit, was obtained when the object had already receded enough to reach magnitude $V \sim 25.5$: NOT was able to detect it with less of an hour of integration time, and the resulting dataset was actually sufficient to reach

$V \sim 26.1$ at a SNR of 5 (under seeing conditions of $\sim 1''$). The resulting astrometry had an astrometric precision of $\pm 0.1''$, an impressive result corresponding to the detection of a ~ 1.2 meter asteroid 3.3 million kilometers away from Earth.

In many cases like the one described here, where effective exposure times of the order of hours are needed, it is often impossible (and nevertheless not advised) to cover such integration times with a single exposure, due for example to tracking irregularities or saturation issues (common when working unfiltered). When this happens, accurate astrometry can still be obtained by taking shorter exposures and combining (stacking) them together, aligning them in a way that ensures that the flux from the target object always falls in the same region of the imaging array. In order to do so, both the motion of the target and an astrometric solution of each individual image are needed, in order to compute the appropriate shifts between frames that are necessary for the stacking process.

5 Future developments and suggestions

As evidenced by the examples and motivations outlined above, a telescope like NOT offers some excellent opportunities for asteroid science. Some of these abilities will become even more crucial in the near future, once new players become active in the field. These are a few examples of interesting capabilities that can be exploited in the future:

- The examples discussed above proved that NOT is capable of obtaining follow-up of faint newly discovered objects. Many such objects will soon routinely be discovered by the upcoming Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST), which will commonly report discoveries that are too faint for follow-up with smaller facilities. In case other dedicated follow-up facilities are not available, or insufficient, NOT can certainly provide coverage.
- The proven flexibility of NOT can be used to obtain rapid observations of high-profile targets (e.g. temporary captures, interstellar objects, impactors or other target requiring fast reaction times).
- NOT also has the capability to observe fast-moving targets during close fly-bys (e.g. the 2029 fly-by of asteroid Apophis), or low-altitude targets (e.g. Atiras, Earth trojans, or comets located at low solar elongation) thanks to its ability to observe as low as 6° over the horizon.
- And of course, NOT can and should participate in international observing campaign for solar system objects, in order to give additional visibility to the telescope in this community.

In addition to these purely astrometric goals, NOT can of course also perform physical characterization of asteroids and comets. This includes the rare capability to perform polarimetric measurements, which allow for an indirect determination of the albedo of an asteroid, and consequently its size.

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